

Phase transfer of polyoxometalate stabilized silver nanoparticles

Shweta Hegde^a, S. S. Joshi^a, Tulsi Mukherjee^b and Sudhir Kapoor^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Pune University, Pune-411 007, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : s_s_hegde@yahoo.com, ssjoshi@chem.unipune.ac.in

^bRadiation & Photochemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai-400 085, India

E-mail : mukherji@barc.gov.in, sudhirk@barc.gov.in *Fax* : 91-22-25505151

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Abstract : Silver nanoparticles synthesized in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF) by chemical reduction in the presence of prefunctionalized polyoxometalate, γ -[SiW₁₀O₃₆(HSC₃H₆Si)₂O]⁴⁻ {[POM(SH)₂]⁴⁻}. The thiol group of [POM(SH)₂]⁴⁻ provides a capping shell around Ag nanoparticles. The formed capped Ag nanoparticles were successfully transferred in to cyclohexane using cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as a phase transfer catalyst. The dispersed nanoparticles were stable for a long period of time (45 days). After the phase transfer Ag nanoparticles could be separated out from the cyclohexane phase in the form of a powder. The hydrophobic particles thus prepared are readily dispersed in solvent like chloroform, toluene, and chlorobenzene without further surface treatment. The particles surface charge was determined by zeta potential measurements and found to be negative. Various spectroscopic techniques such as UV-Vis, FTIR and transmission electron microscopy were utilized to characterize the [POM(SH)₂]⁴⁻ capped silver nanoparticles.

Keywords : Metals, chemical synthesis, electron microscopy, FTIR, zeta potential.

Introduction

Metal nanoparticles in the size regime of 1–100 nm show interesting properties¹. The appearance of surface plasmon absorption band in the visible region for Ag, Au and Cu nanoparticles have been exploited for various applications¹. The physical origin of the surface plasmon absorption band is due to the coherent oscillation of the conduction band electrons induced by the interacting electromagnetic field. The surface plasmon band strongly depends on the size, shape and local environment of the metal nanoparticles^{1–4}.

There are various methods by which metal nanoparticles can be synthesized^{1–10}. Among others chemical reduction method is commonly used due to the ease of preparation of the particles¹. Functional groups such as thiols and amines are generally used to stabilize metal nanoparticles especially of silver and gold¹. Dispersion of colloidal nanoparticles generally undergoes aggregation and hence to stabilize the particles various stabilizers are used^{1–10}. Also, the as-synthesized nanoparticles are often soluble in either the polar phase or non-polar organic phase but not both. To make particles in non-polar

solvents generally phase transfer method is commonly used¹¹. Recently, various approaches have been attempted to form nanoparticles in non polar solvents^{11–18}.

Recently, heteropolyanions (polyoxometalates, POMs) have been exploited to prepare metal nanoparticles^{19–21}. POMs are typical inorganic metal oxide clusters with a wealth of electrical, magnetic and optical properties. As formamide and *N,N'*-dimethylformamide are common solvents used in organic chemistry, attempts have been made recently to prepare metal nanoparticles in these solvents using stabilizers^{6,7}. In this work, we have used prefunctionalized polyoxometalate, γ -[SiW₁₀O₃₆-(HSC₃H₆Si)₂O]⁴⁻ ([POM(SH)₂]⁴⁻), to prepare silver nanoparticles in DMF and subsequently transferred them in various non polar solvents.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and evolution of silver nanoparticles in DMF :

Passivated Ag nanoparticles were prepared by NaBH₄ reduction. Briefly, 10⁻³ M AgNO₃, 5 × 10⁻⁴ M [POM(SH)₂]⁴⁻ was dissolved in 50 mL DMF. Reduction was carried out by the addition of 5 mg of NaBH₄ to 50

mL DMF solution. $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ acts both as a stabilizer and passivating agent. The DMF dispersion of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ shows no characteristic absorption maximum in the range of 300–800 nm. The Ag^+ ions in DMF also do not exhibit an absorption peak in this region. Upon addition of NaBH_4 to the DMF solution containing $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ and AgNO_3 , the color of the solution gradually changed from colorless to dark yellow. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 90 min when most of the nucleation had already occurred. The charge on the surface of the Ag particles was determined to be -32.1 mV by zeta potential measurements. UV-Vis absorption of the solution showed an absorption band with a maximum at 430 nm (spectrum not shown here), which corresponds to a typical plasmon band of Ag nanoparticles¹⁻⁴. The nanoparticles were stable in solution for at least 1 month. Transmission electron micrographs of the Ag nanoparticles in DMF show that the particles are nearly spherical with a mean diameter of 8 ± 4 nm (Fig. 1a). The corresponding electron diffraction pattern is also shown in Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1. (a) Transmission electron micrograph of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles in DMF before phase transfer and (b) the corresponding electron diffraction pattern.

Phase transfer experiments :

Phase transfer experiments were attempted using DMF containing $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles and cyclohexane. The mixture was emulsified for 30 min by vigorous stirring at room temperature. After this the reaction was allowed to proceed. On standing for 1 h, the mixture was transformed from an emulsion into two liquid layers. The lower layer was a colloidal dispersion of Ag nanoparticles in DMF colored dark yellow and the upper layer of cyclohexane remained colorless. This is due to the fact that the $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles are hydrophilic in nature. Therefore, attempt was made to make their surface hydrophobic by

adding cationic stabilizer. For phase transfer experiments 5 mL of the Ag sol in DMF was taken and this was followed by addition of 1.6×10^{-2} M CTAB. The mixture was emulsified for ~ 5 min by vigorous stirring at room temperature. After this the reaction was allowed to proceed. On standing for 1 min, the mixture was transformed from an emulsion into two liquid layers. A vivid transfer of color from the DMF phase to cyclohexane indicated the extraction of Ag metal nanoparticles to cyclohexane layer. The lower layer of DMF became completely colorless and cyclohexane layer became pale yellow in color indicating the transfer of Ag nanoparticles. Zeta potential measurements were carried out for the particles separated in cyclohexane and found to be -0.1 mV. This indicates that hydrophobization of the Ag nanoparticles has taken place. The presence of Ag nanoparticle transferred to cyclohexane was confirmed by the absorption spectrum (Fig. 2a). The TEM image of the particles (Fig. 2b) after the phase transfer shows that the particles are of average size 8 ± 1 nm and no signifi-

Fig. 2. (a) Optical absorption spectrum of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles in cyclohexane after phase transfer and (b) transmission electron micrograph of the silver nanoparticles.

cant change in the size of the particles has occurred after phase transfer. The phase transferred particles are spherical, monodisperse and are equally spaced throughout. There exists a possibility that the addition of CTAB dis-

places the $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ from the surface of the silver particles. To delineate this possibility, the DMF solution after the phase transfer of silver nanoparticles in cyclohexane was heated. No change in the color of the DMF solution was observed. It is known that reduction of POM leads to the development of blue color. As no blue color was observed on heating the DMF solution it indicates that all the $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ get transferred with the Ag nanoparticles to cyclohexane phase. To further substantiate the above arguments, FTIR experiments were carried out. The presence of a covalent link between the $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ and silver nanoparticles can be confirmed by studying the vibrational band of the thiol group. The results are summarized in Table 1.

It can be noted that for both the samples, that is, before and after phase transfer, no sign of the characteristic $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{SH})$ band in the region of 2563 cm^{-1} was observed. This further confirms the participation of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ as well as of thiol groups in the attachment to Ag nanoparticles. The transferred particles in cyclohexane layer were dried under N_2 stream and attempts were made to re-disperse them in different solvents, viz. toluene, chlorobenzene and chloroform. Fig. 3 shows the optical absorption spectra of the Ag nanoparticles redispersed in various solvents. The spectra obtained in toluene, chloroform and chlorobenzene were almost similar. Chloroform proved to be a better solvent for redispersion of Ag nanoparticles. Fig. 4 shows the TEM image of Ag

Table 1. IR frequencies (in cm^{-1}) of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ and $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ passivated Ag nanoparticles in DMF, cyclohexane and chloroform

$[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$	Ag nanoparticles in DMF	Ag nanoparticles in cyclohexane	Ag nanoparticles in chloroform	Frequency assignments
2562	–	–	–	–SH
1379	1385	1385	1385	$\nu(\text{CH})$
1150	1150	1150	1150	$\nu(\text{SiC})$
1082	1090	1090	1089	$\nu(\text{SiO})$
1063	1062	1063	1063	$\nu(\text{CH})$
1041	1040	1039	1039	$\nu(\text{WO})$
902	902	902	902	$\nu(\text{WO})$
860	862	862	864	$\nu(\text{WO})$
806	805	–	806	$\nu(\text{WO})$
540	540	541	542	$\nu(\text{SiO})$
412	410	410	411	$\nu(\text{WO})$

Fig. 3. Optical absorption spectra of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles redispersed in (a) toluene, (b) chloroform and (c) chlorobenzene.

Fig. 4. Transmission electron micrograph of $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles redispersed in chloroform.

The particles were found to be slightly less monodisperse than that obtained

Scheme 1. Schematic showing the formation of surface ion pair between CTAB and surface-bound POM.

in cyclohexane after phase transfer. However the spacing between the particles was almost equal. Particles of two different sizes 2–3 nm and 5–6 nm were obtained. The formation of surface ion pairs due to electrostatically attractive forces is probably the main reason of the CTAB - induced phase transfer of silver nanoparticles. The mechanism is illustrated schematically in Fig. 5. Qualitative evidence of the charge neutralization was obtained by measuring the zeta-potentials of nanoparticles at 25 °C (Table 2). As can be seen, nanoparticles in non-polar solvents have very small negative zeta potential.

Table 2. Zeta potentials for various $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ capped Ag nanoparticles at 25 °C in different solvents

Solvent	Zeta potential (mV)
DMF	-32.1
Cyclohexane	-0.1
Chloroform	1.33

Conclusions

Phase transfer of Ag nanoparticles into cyclohexane is size dependent. Only smaller sized particles were able to transfer in to cyclohexane layer whereas the larger particles settled down at the bottom of the cyclohexane layer. The phase transferred Ag nanoparticles in cyclohexane were found to more monodispersed than that in DMF.

Experimental

All solvents and reagent were used without further purification. Glassware was cleaned using chromic acid before being rinsed with distilled water and Millipore purified water, and dried in an oven at 110 °C.

Materials :

AgNO_3 and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) were obtained from Aldrich. *N,N'*-Dimethylformamide cyclohexane chlorobenzene (Spectrochem, India), chlo-

roform and toluene were of UV spectroscopy grade and obtained from Spectrochem, India. All the chemicals and solvents were used as received.

Synthesis of prefunctionalized polyoxometalate, γ - $[\text{SiW}_{10}\text{O}_{36}(\text{HSC}_3\text{H}_6\text{Si})_2\text{O}]^{4-}$ $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]$ and Ag nanoparticles in DMF by chemical reduction :

The synthesis of the $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ was carried out as per the reported method¹⁹. Briefly, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ AgNO_3 and $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ $[\text{POM}(\text{SH})_2]^{4-}$ was dissolved in 50 mL DMF. Sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , 5 mg) was then added to the above solution and shaken vigorously. The reaction flask was kept aside for 30 min for the reaction to complete.

Characterization :

Samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared by putting a drop of the colloidal solution on a copper grid coated with a thin amorphous carbon film. Samples were dried and kept under vacuum in a desiccator before putting them in a specimen holder. TEM characterization was carried out using a Phillips CM 200 electron microscope. Particle sizes were measured from the TEM micrographs and calculated by taking at least 100 particles. Absorption measurements were carried out on a JascoV-530 spectrophotometer. The spectra were recorded at room temperature using 1 cm quartz cuvette. Zeta potential measurements for determining the charge were carried out using Malvern Instrument, zeta sizer (nanosizer). The FTIR measurements were performed using a Nicolet Nexus 870 Fourier-transform infrared spectrometer.

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